

COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING: ITS IMPACT ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

The study intended to determine the extent of community involvement in the Modular Distance Learning Implementation and ascertain its impact on students' academic success. Specifically, the research ought to find out the following: (1) the extent of community involvement in MDL implementation in terms of classroom home environment, mentoring process, and school initiatives (2) the manifested academic performance in terms of cognitive, affective, and manipulative skills/abilities (3) the relationship between community involvement related factors and students' academic success indicators. A quantitative research design was used to determine community involvement in MDL implementation on student academic success. Moreover, a descriptive correlational design is utilized in the study to ascertain the impact of community involvement in MDL implementation on student academic success. The survey respondents participated by 100 Grade 8 students at Tinurik National High School for the school year 2020-2021. The survey was conducted online through google forms. Results revealed that there is a significant relationship between community involvement-related factors and student academic success. Results also suggest that the school may continually encourage parents, local government units, and private entities to support and participate in the implementation of MDL. In addition to that, teachers should always collaborate with parents to persuade them to become part of their child's learning and participate significantly in implementing school programs and activities. Finally, the researcher suggested conducting Quarterly Meetings with PTA, local barangays, and school administrators to discuss specific concerns and provide feedback on the students' current learning setup. These meetings will allow all participants to become active contributors in assisting the school in shaping a community involvement program that meets the needs of every student in this new learning setup.

Keywords: Modular Distance Learning, involvement, community, student academic success, descriptive-correlational, Philippines